

CSSDM Knowledge Graph to Enable Continuity of Care Data Interoperability

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Abstract—The swift progress of digital technologies and recent global pandemic events have intensified the focus on leveraging these technologies to improve healthcare service delivery and workflow, particularly during crises. Action plans that consolidate existing digital transformation programs are being reviewed to establish core infrastructure for sustainable healthcare solutions. For instance, reforming health and social care to personalize home care can reduce the need for treatment in overcrowded acute hospital settings, improving experiences and outcomes for both healthcare professionals and service users. In this data-driven field, tackling the interoperability challenge through standards-based roadmaps is essential for establishing seamless connections between health and social care services. This strategy ensures secure and reliable data exchange across various healthcare providers.

In this paper, we propose a methodology for extracting, transforming, and loading data through a semi-automated process, utilizing the Common Semantic Standardized Data Model (CSSDM) to build personalized healthcare knowledge graphs (KGs). The CSSDM is based on the formal ontology of ISO 13940 ContSys and integrates FHIR-based specifications to support the structural attributes necessary for KG creation. We propose that the CSSDM facilitates data harmonization and linking, offering an alternative approach to interoperability. This approach promotes a novel form of collaboration between companies developing health information systems and cloud-enabled health services. Consequently, it provides multiple stakeholders with access to high-quality data and information sharing.

Index Terms—Continuity of care, EHR, FHIR, Healthcare System, Interoperability, Ontology, Knowledge Graph

I. INTRODUCTION

The global pandemic has profoundly impacted the operations of service-based industries, with healthcare and social care sectors among those most heavily affected. In response, national health systems are actively working on strategic action plans to incorporate digital solutions as a core aspect of future healthcare and social care infrastructure, aiming for significant integration by 2025 as part of the *National Health Service's* long-term vision. With the rapid advancement of digital plat-

forms, individuals are increasingly relying on technology-driven, home-based solutions to monitor their health and share information with healthcare providers when necessary. However, many of these platforms utilize black-box machine learning (ML) models, raising concerns about the reliability of ML processes due to the lack of transparency and source traceability [1]. Although ML technologies have reached a high level of maturity, their adoption and deployment in healthcare are not as widespread as expected, mainly because of users' lack of trust in Artificial Intelligence systems [2]. To ensure trust and reliability, several initiatives have been enacted, including the *European Union (EU) Artificial Intelligence (AI) Act* in Europe. Ontologies are seen as a crucial approach to enhancing the accountability of ML systems, as they provide structured conceptual models to represent a specific domain. Additionally, ontologies introduce formalism and reasoning capabilities that support more transparent and explainable decision-making processes within these systems.

Knowledge Graphs (KGs) [3] which are generated via mapping and organizing domain data points to an ontology schema [4], [5], offer significant potential for enhancing the management, analysis, and application of Electronic Health Records (EHRs) data. KGs enable the integration of diverse healthcare data sources (e.g., EHRs, lab results, imaging, genomic data) into a unified representation. This promotes interoperability among different healthcare systems and supports the seamless sharing of patient information across institutions. However, without a standard-based ontology schema, KG can not enable continuity of data flow among and across healthcare systems.

A recent paper by Shang, Y et al. (2021) [6] emphasizes the use of KGs to connect various nonclinical data with EHR for better decision-making, offering clear and explainable results to address healthcare queries over time. KGs represent knowledge, relationships, and data entities within a formal ontological framework, providing clarity to healthcare

concepts within the graph. Automatically generated KGs are susceptible to noise and cross-domain data, which can hinder their effectiveness in domain-specific applications [7].

In this paper, we introduce a fusion model and outline steps demonstrating how the Web Ontology Language (OWL) 2 [8], [9] model can facilitate data integration from existing legacy systems through a semi-automated mapping process. Our proposed Common Semantic Standardized Data Model (CSSDM) is aligned with International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 23903:2021-*Health informatics — Interoperability and integration reference architecture — Model and framework* [10] for health informatics, focusing on interoperability and integration.

The CSSDM can be applied in various contexts, including organizations managing healthcare and workflow data, public healthcare data controllers (e.g., the Health Service Executive (HSE) in Ireland, National Services Scotland (NSS), Spanish National Health System (SNS), or the electronic Data Research and Innovation Service (eDRIS)), and services seeking to enhance data preparation processes for research experiments. A key challenge in all these cases is managing data heterogeneity and the repetitive tasks data analysts face to ensure consistent service quality. Additionally, broader issues arise from interoperability challenges with external data sources and collaborating with clients who may not be familiar with local data standards and practices. The remainder of this paper sets in place research conducted on addressing heterogeneity by describing the related work and current challenges in healthcare data modelling, in Section II. In Section III we present our overall methodology and implementation approach in Section IV, and evaluation in Section V and conclude in Section VI with a discussion on future work plans and an example of a generated knowledge graph from our initial development work.

II. RELATED WORKS

Socio-technical theories, such as Actor-Network Theory (ANT) [11], help to analyze the interactions within healthcare networks, while the *quadruple helix model* promotes collaboration among universities, industry, government, and the public sector. Ontology-based [12] information models can formalize and capture complex relationships, integrating schemas using ontological principles to represent knowledge and interactions in healthcare systems. For example, relationships like professional roles (e.g., doctor, patient, nurse), spatial relations (e.g., location, address), applied technologies (e.g., mHealth apps, telemedicine), and performance metrics (e.g., service quality, drug effectiveness) can be managed through a OWL model [8]. In a complex healthcare environment, both social and non-social relationships including spatial relations, organizational structures, and system interactions are essential. By integrating ontological and social principles, we can create a more robust socio-technical system (STS) model that better captures the dynamics of healthcare interactions.

Key challenges in subsequent work emphasize the limited involvement of healthcare professionals in designing and im-

plementing healthcare information models. Most models are developed by Information and Communications Technology (ICT) professionals with minimal input from healthcare experts, making them ICT-driven rather than domain-driven for their intended use [13]. Non-standardized, self-defined data models often struggle with scaling across diverse EHR datasets [14]. Additionally, *Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources* (FHIR) lacks specific implementation guidelines for context or functionality. For example, the FHIR profile used in the USA is not interoperable with the one used by an Indian hospital. This suggests that no native FHIR OWL specification exists for semantic modeling. Although some ongoing projects aim to transform FHIR JSON into JSON-LD and Turtle format, they lack adherence to ontological principles like those in the OntoClean methodology [15] and do not clearly differentiate between structured attributes and classes. In this paper, we focus on addressing these gaps by adopting a collaborative approach, working with ISO’s Health-informatics technical committee, and drawing on experience from the EU Horizon 2020 *interopEHRate* project.

The SemanticHealthNet project [16], an EU healthcare initiative, highlights the value of using the ISO 13940 *Health informatics — System of concepts to support continuity of care* (ContSys) conceptual framework for ontological modeling, but no comprehensive OWL ontology has been developed, with only two brief papers available. Similarly, the Health at Home (H@H) [17] project by the Italian National Research Council provided a mapping table to capture social care based on ContSys and the initial version of HL7 FHIR v1.0, but progress towards creating a data integration model has stalled.

These existing standards, however, do not align with W3C semantic web technologies and linked data [18], which are crucial for creating and maintaining a globally interconnected graph of data. More recently, a paper by Shang et al. (2021) [6] emphasized using knowledge graphs to connect various nonclinical data with electronic health records (EHR) for better decision-making. Knowledge graphs represent knowledge and data entities in a formal ontological structure, making healthcare concepts explicit.

Our goal is to finalize the OWL ontology by building on their scientific analysis, advancing knowledge development, and verifying and testing the implementation of the CSSDM framework. We summarize our methodology and findings in the following section.

Fig. 1. CSSDM Alignment with New EIF

The CSSDM model aligns with the European ISA recom-

mendations on the new *European Interoperability Framework (EIF)* and demonstrates compliance with EIF levels, as shown in Figure 1. The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) provides a legal framework for intergovernmental interoperability. The acronym FAIR stands for data that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. The FAIR principle supports CSSDM’s organizational interoperability, as the model is based on the Web Ontology Language (OWL), enabling a critical semantic interoperability ecosystem. Additionally, CSSDM’s development emphasizes the use of open-source (OS) software and open protocols (Open API), making it neutral and independent of proprietary software. Figure 2 outlines the technical implementation pipeline for CSSDM. The bottom part of the figure showcases that data can originate from various national and regional EHR databases or any existing EHR databases that use open standards such as HL7 FHIR or OpenEHR. The Karma data integration tool is used as a middle layer to transform different data models into the CSSDM model and facilitate data integration. This process aligns perfectly with the ISO 12967-2:2020 Health Informatics — Service Architecture (HISA) framework. Once integrated, the data can be stored in the graph database. Data security and privacy are managed by the implementing company responsible for large-scale system development.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Hypothesis

We initiate our proposed methodology with three key assumptions. The first assumption is that the patient is a key societal value for the future of the healthcare network. If placed at the center of framework design, patient information can lead to sociotechnical systems that enable connectivity between people, professionals, and organizations to achieve the *eHealthcare* vision of interoperability. This would accommodate 360-degree views and facilitate information exchange, thereby ensuring a control program for continuity of life plans. Looking at standards and ontological concept maps such as continuity of care, ISO 13940 (ContSys) [19] provides a framework for patients’ required journeys from one healthcare setting to another. This allows for better planning and model design, highlighting explicit relationships, and reducing frequent hospital admissions and inpatient care, ultimately improving an individual’s overall health and maximizing independent living.

The second assumption is that the project will reuse, redesign, adopt, and adapt several key technologies (such as *knowledge modeling* tools), standards, best practices, architectures (like Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise (*IHE*) Profiles), and protocols that exist today to collect, store, and exchange healthcare data. Additional considerations include how to aggregate and align schemas using different patterns, how to create an interoperable system using a specific language (like RDF/OWL), and how to design a knowledge base that accommodates different terminologies (like SNOMED-CT). Recent German initiative *National Research Data Infrastructure for Personal Health Data (NFDI4Health)* as well as

Fig. 2. Transformation process of different datasets using CSSDM, and AI based data integration tool as a middleware; OS Open Source; HISA Health Informatics Service Architecture; W3C World Wide Web Consortium.

European Committee for Standardization (*Comite’ Europe’ en de Normalisation*) CEN emphasize on reuse and harmonizing of different standards to improve healthcare data interoperability [20].

The third assumption is to involve, implement, engage, educate, and empower healthcare professionals and patients who interact with digital devices daily to record, monitor, and disseminate health records. A standardized data collection and reporting process that ensures data quality is central to successful interoperability. While facilitating access to patients’ personal health data is core to the project, it also ensures the protection of patients’ interests and needs.

B. Alignment with standards and Framework

Top-level ontologies provide a domain-independent conceptual framework, defining categories like Event, Mental Object, and Quality, along with relations and axioms. These elements standardize the upper-level model, facilitating connections between a given ontology and other freely available ontologies such as Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV) [21] and the NCBO Biomedical Ontology [22]. In the CSSDM model, we adopt the Descriptive Ontology for Linguistic and Cognitive Engineering (DOLCE) [23] as a balanced middle-ground solution, combining formalization and complexity for an effective practical application. Despite the advantages of top-level ontologies, their alignment and implementation are complex, requiring expert input. Projects like the EU’s Advancing Clinico-Genomic Trials (ACGT) [24] and others have highlighted the importance and benefits of top-level alignment in healthcare. Recently DOLCE became ISO standards (*ISO/IEC 21838-3:2023 Information technology — Top-level ontologies (TLO) Part 3: Descriptive ontology for linguistic and cognitive engineering (DOLCE)*) [25] guarantees relevance in the international perspective.

Figure 3 presents a partial visualization of CSSDM classes using the WebProte’ge’ tool. The purple elements at the top,

Fig. 3. Alignment of CSSDM with ISO and W3C Standards

such as *mentalObject*, *stative*, and *event*, represent DOLCE classes, with the remaining being domain-specific classes from ISO/DIS 13940 ContSys [19].

In Step 1, we developed a formal ontology for Continuity of Care (CSSDM), with details available in our prior research [26], [27]. During this phase, we reviewed and incorporated existing resources related to continuity of care information models. These included national and regional EHR systems, FHIR resources, and Continuity of Care Record (CCR) models, which were subsequently mapped and translated into a formal OWL model.

In Step 2, we shared, discussed, and disseminated our formal OWL model with both national and international technical committees involved in our project. This collaborative process aimed to establish a consensus on concept mapping based on their meanings. For instance, we aligned “subject of care” with *FHIR:Patient*, “observed condition” with *FHIR:Observation*, and “referral” with *FHIR:ServiceRequest*. However, an exact match for *FHIR:MedicationRequest* was not found in the Contsys resource, leading us to create a subclass under “request” instead. The mapping is available in Table 1.

The expressiveness of our CSSDM ontology model is ALCHQ(D) as per the Description Logic (DL) scale [28]. We have not exploited the full power of DL-full as supported by the OWL-2 language; rather, we used simple rules to make our model compatible with the *GraphDB* rule engine and offer quick query execution times.

Finally, in this section, we provide details on the data structure of the class *observation* and the property *person.gender* in the RDF Turtle syntax. The *observation* class reuses properties defined by *FHIR observation resources*. This facilitates our model to be interoperable and semantically aligned with other EHR models using version FHIR 4.6 specification, which is crucial for cross-border studies on intellectual disability clients

in the future.

The *observation* captures measurements and makes simple assertions about a *patient*, a device, or another subject. The subject of observation is the *patient* class. The performer of the observation is the *healthcare professional* class. A datatype restriction is encapsulated under the property *person.gender*, where data providers must choose among the gender values “Male,” “Female,” or “Transsexual” as it is mandatory and important information needed by service providers. It cannot be left blank, and the reasoner will detect if incorrect information is inserted into the system. The code below demonstrates an example of this observation class detail in RDF Turtle syntax.

```

http://purl.org/net/for-coc#Observation
CoC:Observation rdf:type owl:Class;
rdfs:subClassOf [rdf:type owl:Restriction;
owl:onProperty
observation-definitions:Observation.performer;
owl:someValuesFrom EWS:healthcare_professional],
[rdf:type owl:Restriction;
owl:onProperty observation-definitions:
Observation.subject;
owl:someValuesFrom CoC:Patient];
oboInOwl:hasDbXref
https://www.hl7.org/fhir/observation-definitions.html
#Observation^^xsd:anyURI;
rdfs:comment Measurements and simple assertions
made about a patient, device or
other subject.@en.

```

person.gender(property)

```

https://www.hl7.org/fhir/person-definitions.html#
Person.gender
person-definitions:Person.gender
rdf:type owl:DatatypeProperty;
rdfs:range [rdf:type rdfs:Datatype;
owl:unionOf ([rdf:type rdfs:Datatype;
owl:oneOf [rdf:type rdf:List;
rdf:first Female^^xsd:string;
rdf:rest rdf:nil]]
[rdf:type rdfs:Datatype;

```

ContSys Concept	FHIR Resources
SubjectOfCare:healthcare actor with a person role; who seeks to receive, is receiving, or has received healthcare	FHIR:Patient: Demographics and other administrative information about an individual or animal receiving care or other health-related services.
Observed Condition: health condition observed by a healthcare actor	FHIR:Observation: Measurements and simple assertions made about a patient, device or other subject.
Request: demand for care where a healthcare professional asks a healthcare provider to perform one or more healthcare provider activities	No one to one Mapping available
MedicationRequest (New Subclass)	FHIR: MedicationRequest:An order or request for both supply of the medication and the instructions for administration of the medication to a patient.
Referral	FHIR: ServiceRequest:A record of a request for service such as diagnostic investigations, treatments, or operations to be performed

TABLE I
CONTSYS FHIR MAPPING

```
owl:oneOf [rdf:type rdf:List;
rdf:first Male^^xsd:string;
rdf:rest rdf:nil]]
[rdf:type rdfs:Datatype;
owl:oneOf [rdf:type rdf:List;
rdf:first Transsexual^^xsd:string;
rdf:rest rdf:nil]]];
rdfs:comment gender might not match the biological
sex as determined by genetics.
```

In Step 3, we present a summary of the enriched formal OWL model, which incorporates attributes defined in FHIR resources. Figure 4 provides a snapshot from the Prote’ge’ editor, illustrating the placement of specific concepts within the class hierarchy. For example, *MedicationRequest* is displayed as a subclass of *mentalObject*. The right side of the figure shows attributes derived from FHIR resources, such as *MedicationRequest.note*, *MedicationRequest.status* and *MedicationRequest.dispenseRequest.quantity*.

IV. TECHNICAL IMPLEMENTATION

The first step in the process involves working collaboratively with advanced nurse practitioners, healthcare staff, local IT personnel, and data scientists, to create a demonstrator for data collection. The goal is to design electronic forms capable of capturing healthcare data in a structured format (see Figure 5), transitioning from a “Model of Use” (paper-based forms) to a “Model of Meaning” (a cloud-based demonstrator enabling machine-to-machine communication) [29]. For example, agreed-upon information is broken down into individual data fields rather than clustered into a text box. Address fields are separated into distinct rows, such as Street Name, Apartment Name, etc. (similar to Amazon’s format). When designing these forms, it’s essential to prioritize which terms are core, which are common, and which are context-specific, relevant only to the organization [30]. Once the data is agreed upon and structured, it can be captured in the *demonstrator* see Figure 5 for prototype mobile app develop for Irish Based residential care.

Progress on the CSSDM has been shared with the ISO and CEN community in phases over three years. For example, the release of the formal ontology for continuity of care is complemented by a *blog post* on the project’s website. Figure 2 outlines the technical implementation pipeline for CSSDM, showcasing the tools and methods applied so far. We have also put forward proposals and secured funding opportunities for further data collection. Upon receiving ethical approval, we

plan to gather additional data from various healthcare sources via our designated service. This will be accomplished through planned fieldwork, such as workshops and surveys, which have already proven effective during the early stages of the project.

As the project progressed, the development team used *ontoRefine* [31], a data transformation tool based on *OpenRefine* and integrated into the GraphDB workbench, to clean the collected data. With the expansion of the research program, larger datasets were integrated using *KARMA* [32], an open-source tool designed for data integration from multiple sources such as XML, CSV, text files, and web APIs. KARMA also enabled the creation of Relational Database (RDB) to Resource Description Framework (RDF) mapping language *R2RML* [33], streamlining file mapping for future integration of new or evolving models with updated data. It has a user-friendly user interface (UI) which is easy to use compared to other command line tools such as *D2RQ* [34]. Figure 6 illustrates the process of converting Irish datasets into RDF format using the CSSDM ontology as a common schema.

The tool’s user interface facilitates initial mapping by involving healthcare stakeholders, reducing disagreements and misalignment. This semi-automated process allows for storing the initial mapping file as an *R2RML* file, which can be reused in future processes unless the dataset structure changes.

For our prototype development, we used the free version of *Ototext GraphDB* Version 10.6.2. GraphDB’s access control is implemented using a hierarchical role-based access control (RBAC) model [35], [36], allowing the database administrator to assign specific roles during server setup, such as:

- **ADMIN:** Can perform all operations without restriction.
- **USER:** Can save SPARQL queries, graph visualizations, and user-specific settings.
- **MONITORING:** Allows monitoring operations (queries, updates, abort query/update, resource monitoring).
- **REPO MANAGER:** Can create, edit, and delete repositories, with read and write permissions to all repositories.

GraphDB also supports lightweight directory access protocol (LDAP). Data access control for healthcare data is essential to ensure the security, privacy, and compliance of sensitive health information. The above mentioned access control and protocol ensure the security of the healthcare system by blocking unauthorized third-party access. The CSSDM model can be hosted on a commercial cloud provider such as *Amazon Neptune*, where security measures and safety protocols are

Fig. 4. FHIR: Medication Request attributes inclusion in CSSDM ontology

Fig. 5. Prototype Mobile App for Data Entry and Collection

managed by the provider, like *Amazon Web Services (AWS)*.

The overall safety, data privacy, and reliability of CSSDM implementation depend on the healthcare system operator. In this case, it's managed by *Davra*, an Irish startup responsible for large-scale CSSDM deployment. Davra complies with various regulatory frameworks, including *FedRamp*, *Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA)*, ISO 27001 [37], *Health Information Trust Alliance (HITRUST)* certification, and *NIST 8259 CSF2014* for cloud-based software.

V. EVALUATION OF THE CSSDM MODEL

This phase is highly technical, so the pedagogical emphasis should be on having domain experts, such as healthcare professionals, oversee and validate the query results generated by data scientists within the healthcare organization. Their primary role is to ensure that the outcomes match the expected results based on the specific scenario and align with the initial assumptions made when defining personas.

In a healthcare domain project conducted by the study group, we present various query evaluations. Several SPARQL queries [38] are used to demonstrate that the knowledge graph model effectively addressed key competency queries (CQ) [39], offering valuable insights for future research and analysis. This also highlights how our methodology successfully integrates theory, practice, and interdisciplinarity in a pedagogically effective way. *The supplementary document* provided the results of CQ1 *Select all female patient who visited hospital and prescribe quantity.* and CQ2 *Select all male patient who visited hospital and prescribe quantity.*, demonstrating how to use Google Chart functionality within the GraphDB SPARQL query panel. It shows that the prescribed quantity of specific drugs is higher for male patients than for female patients. Additional CQs and their SPARQL structures are provided in the *supplementary document* available online.

The consistency of the CSSDM ontology was verified using the *HermiT reasoner*, a Prote'ge' plugin that identifies subsumption relationships between classes. Additionally, Description Logic (DL) queries confirmed the model's logical soundness in retrieving information. We also evaluated the CSSDM ontology with the OOPS! ontology pitfall scanner [40], obtaining a result with no pitfalls.

Fig. 6. Semantic Data Mapping using KARMA Data integration tool.

Fig. 7. CSSDM Knowledge Graph depicted specific care plan

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We define healthcare data interoperability as a continuous process rather than a one-off task, especially in the fast-changing ICT landscape. In this paper, we propose a significant step towards addressing the interoperability challenge by adapting existing models and techniques to align with the Linked Data approach, ultimately creating an interconnected knowledge graph. As shown in Figure 7, GraphDB pattern matching aids in building such a graph. Figure 7 depicts a personalized care plan of the patient (ID 3219044L) Mary Smith and it's associated with the episode of care 147, with the active medication *Ibuprofen*, instruction of dosage route (i.e. Oral). Knowledge graphs facilitate more efficient handling of complex queries compared to traditional join operations in relational databases.

In the second phase of the project, we have added a total of 171 data properties related to *social determinants of health (SDH)*. SDH refer to the non-clinical factors that affect health outcomes. These include the environments in

which individuals are born, raised, work, and age, as well as the broader economic, social, and political systems that shape these living conditions. The rationale behind collecting SDH information only as true or false (i.e. boolean datatype) as this type of data is sensitive personal information with significant privacy and security considerations [41]. The latest version of CSSDM OWL ontology is available on Biportal ContSonto. Furthermore, we will focus on evaluating user satisfaction by leveraging user experience (UX) dimensions from previous research on the Semantic User Interface (SemUI) [42]. Our future goal is to test the model using a large dataset, specifically the *MIMIC-IV* free clinical dataset and one regional dataset from *Hospital Recoletas Salud Zamora*, Spain. The final stage involves deploying the system on a cloud server with the support of our industry partner, *Davra*, and conducting performance testing of the CSSDM platform.

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